

COPING WITH JOB INSECURITY: EXAMINING ANXIETY, FINANCIAL SECURITY, AND SOCIAL SUPPORT AMONG CONTRACT WORKERS IN THE PHILIPPINE GOVERNMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the resource management and stress mitigation factors among contract workers in the Philippine government through the lens of the Conservation of Resources (COR) theory. Using a quantitative research design, data were collected via an online survey from 162 contract workers from various government offices. The survey instruments included the Anxiety Self-Rating Scale, Financial Security Scale, Social Support Questionnaire (ISEL-Short Version), and Coping Scale. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics, bivariate correlations, and multi-linear regression analysis using SPSS version 20. The results indicated that financial security did not significantly correlate with anxiety and coping strategies. However, tangible support, a subscale of social support, showed a significant negative correlation with anxiety, emphasizing the importance of practical support in reducing anxiety levels. Other subscales of social support, such as appraisal and belonging, did not show significant correlations with anxiety and coping strategies. These findings highlight the necessity of enhancing tangible support to mitigate anxiety among contract workers. The study underscores the need for comprehensive support programs that include practical assistance to address the psychological impacts of job insecurity. Future research should explore these relationships further with larger samples and in different sectors to generalize the findings.

Keywords: *Job insecurity, anxiety, financial security, social support, coping strategies, contract workers*

INTRODUCTION

The shifting dynamics of employment have increasingly subjected workers to job insecurity, including those in contractual positions. This phenomenon is exacerbated by global economic uncertainties, technological advancements, and organizational restructuring (Shoss, 2017). Contract workers in the Philippine government are no exception, experiencing heightened anxiety as their contract termination dates approach. This study aims to assess the levels of anxiety and the coping strategies employed by these workers, contributing to a deeper understanding of how these mechanisms can mitigate the psychological impacts of job insecurity.

Recent research emphasizes the significant role of job insecurity as a stressor in the modern workforce. Job insecurity is defined as the perceived threat to the continuity and stability of employment as it is currently experienced (Shoss, 2017). This phenomenon has been associated with several negative effects, including mental distress, reduced job satisfaction, and decreased organizational commitment (Sverke, Hellgren, & Näswall, 2006).

Research highlights the significance of coping strategies in managing job insecurity. Coping involves constantly adjusting cognitive and behavioral efforts to handle specific internal and external demands perceived as overwhelming (Giunchi, Vonthron, & Ghislieri, 2019). Coping strategies are typically categorized into problem-focused and emotion-focused strategies. Problem-focused coping involves addressing the root cause of stress directly, while emotion-focused coping seeks to alleviate the emotional distress associated with the stressor (Giunchi et al., 2019).

Several studies have explored the coping strategies employed by individuals facing job insecurity. For instance, recent research has identified proactive coping behaviors, such as job search behaviors, organizational citizenship behaviors (OCB), and impression management, as common strategies used by employees to manage job insecurity (Nath et al., 2024; Sora et al., 2013). These strategies can significantly influence an individual's psychological well-being and their ability to adapt to stressful situations (Giunchi et al., 2019; Nath et al., 2024).

Moreover, financial security and social support have been identified as critical factors in mitigating the negative impacts of job insecurity. Financial security can reduce anxiety by providing a buffer against economic uncertainties, while social support can enhance emotional resilience by offering a sense of belonging and security (Bhowmick, Padhi, & Pattnaik, 2022; Patterson, 2003). This study aims to explore the relationship between these factors and the anxiety levels experienced by contract workers in the Philippine government.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in the Conservation of Resources (COR) theory, which suggests that individuals strive to obtain, retain, and protect their resources. When these

resources are threatened or lost, stress ensues (Hobfoll, 1989). Job insecurity represents a significant threat to these resources, triggering anxiety and necessitating coping strategies to manage this stress.

Research Gap and Rationale

Despite extensive research on job insecurity, there needs to be more focus on the unique context of government contract workers in the Philippines. These workers often face uncertain rehiring, and delayed contracts or salaries, further exacerbating their stress and anxiety. This study addresses this gap by examining how financial security and social support influence anxiety and coping strategies in this specific population. The researchers of this study hypothesize that financial security and social support play crucial roles in mitigating anxiety among contract workers.

Research Questions

1. Does financial security influence anxiety levels and coping mechanisms of government contract workers?
2. Does social support system influence the levels of anxiety and the effectiveness of coping mechanisms among government contract workers?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted among contract workers in various government agencies in the Philippines, encompassing both local and national levels. A total of 59 offices participated, including 53 local government units and 6 national agencies. The participants ($N = 162$) comprised of (44%) males and (56%) were females, all on one-year contracts. The majority of participants (72%) were between the ages of 21 and 45, 27% were between 45 and 65, and a small percentage (2%) were aged 67 and 70.

Data Gathering Procedure

The participants were selected using an online survey method, ensuring that contract workers from various government agencies, including local government units such as cities and municipalities, and national government agencies, could participate, resulting in a wide and diverse pool of respondents. The study involved contract workers in the Philippines, aged 18 to 65 years, with diverse educational backgrounds.

Informed consent was collected from all participants prior to their involvement in the study. The survey ran from May 22, 2024, until June 8, 2024. Before participating, respondents were provided with detailed information about the study, including its purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. This information was presented in an online consent form, which participants had to read thoroughly. They were informed

of their rights, including the right to withdraw from the study at any time without any negative consequences. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained, with assurances that their identities would not be disclosed and that the data collected would be used solely for research purposes. Participants indicated their consent and interest to participate by entering their email address in the online form, thus confirming their voluntary participation in the study.

Instruments Used

The study utilized several validated instruments to measure key variables such as anxiety, financial security, social support, and coping strategies.

The **Anxiety Self-Rating Scale** is a psychological assessment tool designed to measure the severity of anxiety symptoms in individuals. It is a self-report questionnaire that enables individuals to reflect on their experiences and rate the frequency and intensity of their anxiety symptoms. Adapted from the Zung Self-Rating Anxiety Scale (SAS), this scale comprises 10 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 0 (never) to 4 (always). The scores range from 0 to 40, with higher scores indicating higher levels of anxiety (Dunstan, D. A., & Scott, N. (2020)). The instrument demonstrated good reliability in this study, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.82.

The **Financial Security Scale** is a self-report instrument designed to measure an individual's perception of their financial stability and security. Adapted from Munyon, Carnes, Lyons, and Zettler (2024), it consists of 5 items rated on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). Higher scores on the scale indicate greater perceived financial security, allowing researchers to quantify and interpret an individual's financial stability effectively. This scale has been tested for reliability and validity in previous studies, with a Cronbach's alpha (α) of 0.91, indicating good internal consistency (Munyon et al., 2024).

The **Social Support Questionnaire - Interpersonal Support Evaluation List (ISEL-Short Version)** is a self-report measure designed to assess the perceived availability of social support across different domains. Adapted from Cohen, Mermelstein, Kamarck, and Hoberman (1985), it includes 12 items divided into three subscales (Appraisal, Belonging, and Tangible Support) rated on a 4-point scale ranging from 1 (definitely false) to 4 (definitely true). Higher scores on each subscale indicate greater perceived support in that domain, providing a comprehensive assessment of an individual's social support network. The scale has been validated for internal consistency and constructs validity, with a Cronbach's alpha (α) of 0.82 (Merz et al., 2014).

The **Coping Scale**, adapted from Hamby, Grych, and Banyard (2013), is a self-report measure designed to assess coping strategies across different domains. It includes 13 items categorized into problem-focused and emotion-focused strategies, rated on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (not true about me) to 4 (mostly true about me). Higher scores indicate more frequent use of coping strategies, allowing for an assessment of how individuals manage stress and adversity. The scale was tested for reliability and validity with a Cronbach's alpha (α) of 0.91 (Hamby et al., 2013).

Data Analysis

Quantitative data analysis was performed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, and frequency distributions, were calculated to describe the sample characteristics and key variables. Pearson correlation coefficients were computed to examine the relationships between job insecurity, anxiety, financial security, social support, and coping strategies. Finally, a multi-linear regression analysis was conducted to test the influence of job insecurity on anxiety.

Scope and Limitations

The scope of the study is limited to contract workers in government agencies in the Philippines. The findings may not be generalizable to contract workers in other sectors or countries. The self-reported nature of the survey may also introduce response biases, despite assurances of anonymity.

RESULTS

TABLE 1: Descriptive Statistics and Correlations for Study Variables

Variable	N	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Financial	162	15.48	6.41	-	.098	.104	.075	.087	.037
2. Appraisal Support	162	11.60	2.54	.098	-	.621**	.636**	-.183*	.047
3. Belonging Support	162	11.20	2.35	.104	.621**	-	.501**	-.117	-.031
4. Tangible Support	162	11.72	2.09	.075	.636**	.501**	-	-.196*	-.073
5. Anxiety	162	11.48	6.10	.087	-.183*	-.117	-.196*	-	-.025
6. Coping	162	2.99	.484	.037	.047	-.031	-.073	-.025	-

Note: * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Scores on each scale were computed, and the descriptive statistics are presented in Table 2. The mean score for financial security is 15.48 ($SD= 6.41$), indicating that the participant's financial security is moderately secured, as their scores are around the midpoint. The mean score of their anxiety is 11.48 ($SD= 6.10$), suggesting that the participants are experiencing mild anxiety. Scores on the Social Support Scale were categorized into three subscales: Appraisal with a mean score of 11.60 ($SD=2.54$), Tangible with a mean of 11.72 ($SD= 2.09$), and Belonging with a mean score of 11.20 ($SD= 2.35$). The mean scores for these subscales indicate that they have lesser perceived Social Support in all three dimensions, as their scores are below the mean. Furthermore, scores on the Coping Scale have a mean score of 2.99 ($SD = .484$). This indicates that participants have lower scores on the said test, suggesting a lower level of coping.

As shown in the correlation Table 1 Bivariate correlations were conducted in each variable to check the relation between the predictor variables and criterion variable. Analysis shown that Financial Security is not correlated to Anxiety ($r = .270, p = .087, N = 162$). Similarly, with Financial Security is not also correlated to Coping ($r = .641, p = .037, N = 162$). This means that that having stable finances does not necessarily influence the anxiety and coping level of the participant, suggesting that other factors may significantly contribute on these factors.

Social Support and its subscales to Anxiety results shown the table that the subscales Appraisal ($r = .020, p = -.183, N = 162$), and Tangible support ($r = .013, p = -.196, N = 162$) are correlated to Anxiety. On the other hand, the subscale Belonging Support is not correlated to Anxiety ($r = .138, p = -.117, N = 162$). This means while Belonging Support does not influence the Anxiety level of the participants, results indicated that Appraisal and Tangible Support are effective on this context. Finally, Social Support and its Subscales the Appraisal Support ($r = .557, p = .47, N = 162$), Belonging Support ($r = .691, p = -.031, N = 162$), and Tangible Support ($r = .356, p = -.073, N = 162$) were not correlated to Coping. It implies that having a social support does not necessarily enhance an individual's ability to manage stress, indicating that coping mechanisms may rely more on personal attributes or other external factors.

TABLE 2: Regression Table

Source	<i>B</i>	<i>SE B</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Appraisal	-.235	.241	-.098	-.978	-.183
Tangible	-.388	.293	-.133	-1.325	-.196

Note: $R^2 = .044$

A linear regression was calculated to predict anxiety based on Tangible Support. A significant regression equation was found in Appraisal and Tangible Support ($F(2, 160) = 3.664, p = .028$), with an R^2 of .044. The regression equation indicates that for each unit increase in Appraisal Support, the Anxiety score decreases by -.235, and for each unit increase in Tangible Support, the Anxiety score decreases by -.388. This suggests that both appraisal and tangible support are significant predictors of lower anxiety levels among government contract workers.

DISCUSSION

The study's findings reveal that financial security does not significantly influence anxiety levels among contract workers in the Philippine government. Despite the common assumption that financial stability is crucial for mental well-being, the results indicate that financial security alone may not be the primary determinant of anxiety in this context. This suggests that improving financial security may not be sufficient to reduce anxiety levels, pointing to the need for a broader approach in addressing mental health issues among contract workers (Kim & von dem Knesebeck, 2015; Selenko & Batinic, 2013).

In contrast, social support, particularly appraisal and tangible support, significantly influences anxiety levels among contract workers. The results show that higher levels of these types of support are associated with lower anxiety levels. This finding underscores the importance of a supportive work environment where employees feel valued and assisted. Previous research supports this claim, highlighting that social support in the workplace significantly reduces stress and anxiety (Taylor, 2012). More recent studies by Uchino (2009) emphasize the role of social support in enhancing psychological well-being. This practical approach can significantly reduce anxiety levels and improve overall well-being among contract workers. Theoretically, this aligns with the Conservation of Resources (COR) theory, which posits that bolstering resources through organizational support reduces stress (Hobfoll et al., 2018).

However, the study found no significant correlation between social support and coping mechanisms. This suggests that while social support can effectively reduce anxiety, it does not necessarily improve coping strategies. Although the relationship between social support and anxiety reduction is well-documented (Taylor et al., 2021; Ozbay et al., 2007), there is limited research directly examining the impact of social support on coping mechanisms. Thus, this finding highlights a gap in the existing literature and suggests the need for further research to explore how social support influences coping strategies.

Overall, the study underscores the complex interplay between financial security, social support, anxiety, and coping mechanisms. While financial security alone does not significantly mitigate anxiety or enhance coping, strong social support, particularly tangible and appraisal support, plays a crucial role in reducing anxiety. This highlights the importance of a multifaceted approach to employee well-being that incorporates robust social support systems alongside financial stability. By understanding and addressing these dynamics, government agencies can better support their contract workers, leading to improved mental health and productivity.

Theoretical Implications

These findings contribute to the theoretical understanding of job insecurity and coping by highlighting the nuanced roles of different types of support. The Conservation of Resources (COR) theory posits that individuals strive to obtain, retain, and protect their resources, and when these resources are threatened or lost, stress ensues (Hobfoll, 1989). The significant role of tangible support in reducing anxiety among contractual workers supports the idea that practical resources are vital for managing job insecurity.

Empirical evidence extends our understanding of the COR theory by demonstrating that not all forms of support are equally effective in reducing stress. For instance, while tangible support significantly reduces anxiety, appraisal support, which involves evaluative feedback and encouragement, also plays a crucial role. This finding aligns with recent studies suggesting that different types of social support can buffer against the adverse effects of job insecurity in various ways.

Additionally, the lack of significant correlation between social support and coping mechanisms suggests that while support systems are effective in mitigating anxiety, they do not directly enhance coping strategies. This implies that the COR theory might need to be expanded to account for the complexity of coping mechanisms, which appear to be influenced more by personal traits and individual resilience than by external support alone.

Furthermore, the findings suggest that financial security, often considered a crucial resource, may not directly alleviate anxiety or improve coping strategies among contract workers. This challenges the traditional understanding within the COR framework that resource gain directly correlates with stress reduction. Instead, it highlights the importance of a comprehensive approach that includes both resource provision and the development of personal coping skills.

Practical Implications

The results suggest that interventions aimed at reducing anxiety among contractual workers should focus on enhancing tangible support. Practical assistance, such as providing financial aid, resources for daily living, and material support, could significantly alleviate anxiety. Organizations and policymakers should consider implementing programs that offer tangible support to contractual workers to help mitigate the adverse effects of job insecurity.

Conclusions

This study sought to understand the influences of financial security and social support on anxiety levels and coping mechanisms among contract workers in the Philippine government. Addressing the first research question, the findings reveal that financial security does not significantly impact anxiety levels or coping strategies. This suggests that financial stability alone may not be sufficient to address the mental health needs of contract workers. Theoretically, this challenges the traditional view within the Conservation of Resources (COR) theory that resource gain directly correlates with stress reduction. Practically, it implies that interventions solely focused on improving financial security may not effectively reduce anxiety or enhance coping mechanisms among these workers. A more comprehensive approach that includes the development of personal coping skills and resilience is necessary.

The second research question focused on the role of social support in influencing anxiety levels and coping mechanisms. The study found that social support, particularly appraisal and tangible support, significantly reduces anxiety levels among contract workers. This underscores the importance of a supportive work environment where employees feel valued and assisted. Government agencies should prioritize enhancing social support systems, focusing on practical assistance and constructive feedback to mitigate anxiety effectively. However, the lack of significant correlation between social support and coping mechanisms indicates that while support systems are effective in reducing anxiety, they do not necessarily enhance coping strategies. This suggests that

interventions aimed at improving coping mechanisms need to incorporate specific training in coping techniques and programs designed to build individual resilience.

Recommendations

A holistic approach to well-being is essential. Government agencies should develop integrated wellness programs that combine financial support, social support, and personal development. Regular monitoring of employee well-being and feedback mechanisms should be implemented to assess the effectiveness of the support programs. Surveys, focus groups, and one-on-one meetings can provide valuable insights into employee needs and the impact of implemented programs.

Future research should further explore the nuanced roles of different types of support in managing job insecurity and stress. Researchers should examine the varying levels of anxiety that contract workers experience and how these are influenced by different support mechanisms.

Moreover, future studies should control for the longevity of contract service as a variable, as the duration of contract work may influence participants' behavior and ability to adjust to their situations over time. Understanding how contract workers adapt across different contract lengths could shed light on long-term strategies for improving their mental health and coping mechanisms.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers of this study ensured total compliance with ethical standards throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, who were clearly informed about the nature, purpose, and procedures of the study. Respondents were assured of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. Anonymity was strictly maintained by ensuring that no identifying information was collected or disclosed, thereby safeguarding the privacy and confidentiality of the respondents. The well-being of all respondents was a top priority, and measures were taken to ensure that participation did not cause any harm or distress.

There were no conflicts of interest in the conduct of this study. The researchers adhered to strict anti-plagiarism policies, ensuring that all sources were properly cited and that original research was conducted. The interpretation of the findings was conducted objectively, without bias, and the results were used solely for research purposes. This adherence to ethical standards guarantees the integrity and credibility of the study.

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